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The Merkel Cell Polyomavirus early region activates IL-11.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Small DNA tumor viruses include the human papillomaviruses (HPVs), and polyomaviruses BK, JC and simian virus 40 (SV40), and Merkel Cell Polyomavirus (MCP). While functions of E1 and E2 early genes of HPV16 have been characterized, the functions of Merkel Cell Polyomavirus virus early gene segments are less well understood. We measured total gene expression following expression of the Merkel Cell Polyomavirus early region in human cells. We describe here activation of the cytokine interleukin-11 by the MCP early region.

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